

**TO STUDY TOOL WEAR MECHANISM OF PCD 1600 GRADE ON MACHINING Al-SiC
COMPOSITES
USING
ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS**

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ABSTRACT:

The effect of machining parameters on Tool Wear, Surface Finish and Power Consumed relationship of Aluminium Silicon carbide (Al-SiC)(10P) when machined with PCD (When carbon particles are subjected to high pressure and high temperature they form grains which are called artificial diamonds, these diamonds when sintered together form Poly Crystal Diamond) insert (1600 grade) has been studied here and results have been discussed by correlating parameters with Artificial Neural Network (ANN). This paper presents the optimum machining condition of machining Al-SiC metal matrix composite (MMC) by considering Tool wear and Surface finish. The worn out tool has also been analyzed and the parameters are correlated with ANN by giving three input parameters and predicting three output parameters by training the network using Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN). The result provides some very useful information.

Key words: Machinability, Metal matrix composite, Tool wear, Metal removal rate, Surface Finish, Artificial Neural Network.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Metal matrix composites (MMC) are being used to replace conventional materials in many applications, especially in the automobile and aerospace industries. Aluminium alloy reinforced with ceramic particles is the most popular MMC in the present industry. These low cost composites provide higher strength, stiffness

and fatigue resistance [1, 2, 3] with a minimal increase in density over the base alloy. Owing to the addition of reinforcing materials, which are normally harder and stiffer than the matrix, machining becomes significantly more difficult than in the case of conventional materials, as reported in the earlier publications [1-5]. The Al-SiC (250 Mesh) MMC with hardness 81 BHN (Brinell hardness number) is used for machining. The microstructure and the composition are shown in Fig-1 and Table-1 respectively.

Fig. 1. Microstructure of the work piece (Al-SiC).

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE:

The Al-SiC (MMC) of diameter 55 mm * 300 mm long was machined with PCD (1600 grade) cutting insert at three different cutting speeds (200,300&400 m/min) with a feed rate of 0.075 mm/rev. The depth of cut is kept constant at 0.5 mm. Table- 2 summarize the details of the experimental conditions. The use of PCD cutting insert in this study is due to its excellent performance compared to Carbide cutting inserts and High-speed steel tool while machining Aluminium Silicon carbide [6,7,8].

The surface roughness and tool wear was measured at predetermined intervals. The 2-wattmeter method was used to measure the Power consumed.

3. BACK GROUND OF ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK (ANN):

ANN is used to simulate the machining procedure under various combinations of cutting conditions. These conditions are arrived by setting the weights and giving our outputs as inputs for the network to be trained.

Fig. 2. General Configuration of neural networks.

Fig-2 shows the general configuration of a neural network. The network once trained simulates the machining process and gives us more accurate values when tested with other required parameter values.

4. EXPECTED CONCLUSIONS:

The Trained network is expected to predict the output values very close to the obtained values with minimal error. It is possible to get accurate values by training the network with greater number of samples and more no of iterations. However the optimum conditions for

obtaining an excellent Surface finish, low Tool wear and low Power consumption can be predicted only after completion of our final year project due in 2 months.

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Al	Si	Mg	Mn	Fe	Ti	Ni	Zn	Pb	Sn	Cr	V	Zr
85.9	7.774	0.340	0.043	0.817	0.009	0.085	0.654	0.073	0.154	0.072	0.020	0.003

Table. 1. Chemical composition of the MMC.

Work piece Material	Direct Chill Cast A356/SiC/10p; 55mm Dia x 300 mm long billet
Machine	CNC-LAL2
Tool Insert	CNMA 120408, Nose Radius 0.8mm
Holder Size	25x25 (PCLNR 2525, M12)
Surface Texture Equipment	Surf Test - 301, Make: Mitutoyo
Cutting Parameters	Cutting Speed : 200/300/400 m/min Feed Rate : 0.075 mm/rev , Depth Of Cut : 0.5 mm

Table. 2. Experimental conditions.